

Extraction of Rhenium (VII) with Laurylpyridinium Chloride

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Laurylpyridinium chloride (LP⁺Cl⁻) with its large univalent cation is expected to be a good extractant for perrhenate ion. It is, therefore, of interest to study the extraction of rhenium (VII) with LP⁺Cl⁻. In the present investigation, the extraction of rhenium (VII) with LP⁺Cl⁻ into organic solvents has been studied under wide range of experimental conditions with a view to throw light on the mechanism of the extraction process.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals and Apparatus: Commercially available laurylpyridinium chloride of 99% purity was employed in all extraction experiments. Its purity was checked by estimating chloride. Other chemicals and solvents used were of A.R. grade. Double distilled water was employed to prepare standard solutions. Rhenium in the stock solution was estimated by the nitron method¹. Radioactive Re¹⁸⁶ was obtained by irradiating extra pure rhenium metal with thermal neutrons in Apsara or CIRUS reactor at the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay. Irradiated rhenium metal was dissolved in minimum quantity of nitric acid, and the nitrate ions were expelled by gentle evaporation with HCl on a water bath. The solution was diluted to a known volume with distilled water. The radiochemical purity of the irradiated rhenium was ascertained by measuring the gamma-spectrum and by determining the half-life of the sample. The activity was measured either on a gamma-ray spectrometer provided with a single channel pulse-height analyzer and a well-type 3.8 cm × 3.8 cm NaI (Tl) crystal detector or on a thin (2.5 mg./cm²) and window type G.M. counter in operation with a Dekatron Scaler, a high-voltage unit and a present timer. Corrections for background, coincidence loss, self-absorption and self-scattering were applied, whenever found to be necessary².

Extraction Procedure: Potassium perrhenate solution containing 40–1200 μg of rhenium labelled with Re-¹⁸⁶ was taken in a 125-ml separatory funnel. The pH of the solution was adjusted with HCl or NaOH solution, keeping the total volume of the solution to 20 ml. The solution was then equilibrated for 2 minutes with 20 ml of nitrobenzene containing LP⁺Cl⁻. The two phases were separated and after centrifugation, the activity of 3 ml of each phase was measured. The pH of the equilibrated aqueous phase was noted. The extraction coefficient was calculated with the help of the relation

$$E = \frac{\text{Activity in 3 ml of nitrobenzene}}{\text{Activity in 3 ml of aqueous phase}}$$

1. W. W. Scott, 'Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis', Vol. I, D. Van Nostrand and Co., New York (1939).
2. W. F. Nervik and P. C. Stevenson, *Nucleonics*, 1952, **10**, 18.

pH measurements were taken with a Elico pH meter LI-10 of Electronic and Instruments Co., Hyderabad. The pH meter was calibrated with buffer solutions of pH 4.1 (potassium hydrogen phthalate) and 9 (borax).

A Toshniwal conductivity bridge type CHO 1.02 provided with an audiofrequency oscillator and a sensitive magic eye detector were used for conductivity measurements. All conductance measurements were taken at room temperature. The cell constant of the conductivity cell used was 0.469.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The extraction of rhenium (VII) into nitrobenzene with LP^+Cl^- is better than 99.9% over the pH range 1.5 to 11.1. The extraction coefficient (E) values at different pH are given in Table I. The extraction equilibrium between nitrobenzene phase and aqueous phase is reached within one minute and the separation of the two phases is rapid.

TABLE I

Effect of pH on the Extraction of Re (VII) with LP^+Cl^- in Nitrobenzene

Initial Concentration of Re (VII)	= $1.074 \times 10^{-5} M$
Initial Concentration of LP^+Cl^- in nitrobenzene	= $1.074 \times 10^{-3} M$
Volume of each phase	= 20 ml.
Temperature	= $31^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

pH	Extraction Coefficient (E)	Extraction %
1.5	1590	99.93
2.9	3191	99.95
3.9	6856	99.97
4.5	5070	99.97
5.0	3134	99.97
6.3	2698	99.95
9.3	2262	99.95
11.1	1827	99.93

The composition of the extracted species has been determined by the method of substoichiometric extraction³ of rhenium (VII) with LP^+Cl^- in nitrobenzene at pH 3.9. The substoichiometric extraction was carried out as follows: Solutions containing increasing amounts of potassium perrhenate carrier labelled with Re^{186} were taken in separatory funnels, adjusted to pH 3.9 (total volume = 20 ml) and extracted with 20 ml of 0.0073% solution of LP^+Cl^- in nitrobenzene for two minutes. After the separation of the two phases, the

3. J. Ruzicka and J. Stary, *Atomic Energy Review, I.A.E.A., Vienna, 1964, 2, 3,*

organic extracts were measured and plotted against the amount of rhenium taken. The plot (Figure 1) of the activity against the initial amount of rhenium in the aqueous solution showed a satisfactory linear relationship till rhenium (VII) was subequivalent to the reagent added. A break occurred at the point corresponding to perrhenate : LP^+Cl^- equal to 1 : 1, which may be interpreted to indicate that the extracted species contains perrhenate ion and LP^+ in the proportion of 1 : 1. After reaching this point, the amount of perrhenate extracted into the organic phase remained constant. This experiment also confirmed that the time of two minutes for reaching extraction equilibrium was adequate.

Fig. 1. Substoichiometric extraction of $Re(VII)$ into nitrobenzene with LP^+Cl^- . 1.24 mg of KRe^+O_4 per ml.

The extraction of rhenium (VII) into organic solvents from aqueous solution at pH 3.9 decreases in the series;

Solvent : Nitrobenzene > Methyl isobutyl ketone > Chloroform >

E (6186) (460) (58)

Methyl ethyl ketone > Ethyl acetate > *n*-Amyl alcohol >

E (56) (42) (20)

Iso-Amyl alcohol = Amyl acetate > Octanol > Butanol >

E (18) (18) (11) (7)

Benzene > Xylene > Carbon tetrachloride.

E (0.65) (0.20) (0.13)

The maximum extraction coefficient value of rhenium (VII) for nitrobenzene, a solvent of high dielectric constant ($\epsilon = 36.1$ at 20°), indicates that rhenium (VII) is most probably

extracted as ion pairs. However, the extraction order does not follow the order given by the dielectric constant (ϵ) of the solvents employed, which is as indicated below :

	Solvent : Nitrobenzene	Methyl ethyl ketone	n-Butanol
ϵ (at 20°)	(36.1)	(18.51)	(17.8)
	n-Amyl alcohol	Iso-Amyl alcohol	Methyl isobutyl ketone
ϵ	(15.8)	(14.7)	(13.1)
	Octanol	Ethyl acetate	Amyl acetate
ϵ	(10.3)	(6.4)	(5.07)
	Chloroform		
ϵ	(4.81)		
	Xylene	Benzene	Carbon tetrachloride.
ϵ	(2.56)	(2.28)	(2.23)

Chloroform occupies a very high position in the extraction series though its dielectric constant is very low. This suggests that besides dielectric constant, other properties of the solvents are also involved in determining the extraction of rhenium (VII) with LP^+Cl^- .

Fig. 2. Extraction of Re (VII) into carbon tetrachloride from aqueous solution containing LP^+Cl^- at pH 3.9

The extraction of rhenium (VII) into CCl_4 from aqueous solution of pH 3.9 shows a first power dependence (Fig. 2) on the equilibrium concentration of LP^+Cl^- . Assuming that in aqueous solution of pH 3.9, LP^+Cl^- exists as LP^+ and Cl^- , the nett extraction equilibrium may be represented as

and

$$K_{CCl_4} = \frac{(LP^+ ReO_4^-)_o}{(ReO_4^-)(LP^+)} = \frac{E}{(LP^+)} \quad \dots (1)$$

where subscript (o) signifies organic phase and terms in parenthesis represent concentrations. The extracted species is presumed to remain undissociated in CCl_4 , the dielectric constant of which is very low. The stoichiometry of the extraction (Fig. 3) of perrhenate into chloroform resembles very close to that of extraction into CCl_4 . The log K values of the extraction equilibrium constants at 31° for CCl_4 and CHCl_3 are 0.07 ± 0.01 and 4.34 ± 0.08 respectively.

Fig. 3. Extraction of Re (VII) into chloroform from aqueous solution containing LP^+Cl^- at pH 3.9.

Molecular weight determination gives evidence in support of the dissociation of laurylpyridinium chloride in nitrobenzene. Conductivity measurements with nitrobenzene solution of LP^+Cl^- show that the molar conductance (20.0–26.0 mhos) of its dilute solution ($50\text{--}5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) corresponds to that of 1 : 1 type of electrolytes, though it conducts ($M = 3\text{--}12.3$ mhos) poorly in the concentration range $500\text{--}200 \times 10^{-4} M$. Therefore, it seems reasonable to assume that in dilute nitrobenzene solution $\text{LP}^+\text{ReO}_4^-$ also behaves like 1 : 1 electrolytes⁴.

In the extraction of rhenium (VII) with LP^+Cl^- in nitrobenzene, it is necessary to consider the dissociation of the extracted species into LP^+ and ReO_4^- . The extraction equilibrium may be written as

and the extraction equilibrium constant (K_1) is given by

$$K_1 = \frac{(\text{ReO}_4^-)_o (\text{LP}^+)_o}{(\text{ReO}_4^-) (\text{LP}^+)} = E \times \frac{(\text{LP}^+)_o}{(\text{LP}^+)} \quad \dots (2)$$

The extraction of LP^+Cl^- into nitrobenzene may be represented as

4. R. A. Robinson and R. H. Stokes, 'Electrolytic Solutions', London, Butterworths Scientific Publications (1959).

and the equilibrium is governed by the relation

$$K_2 = \frac{(LP^+)_0 (Cl^-)_0}{(LP^+) (Cl^-)} \quad \dots (3)$$

where K_2 = equilibrium constant. By combining equations (2) and (3) and utilizing the expression of electroneutrality in the organic phase, $(LP^+)_0 = (ReO_4^-)_0 + (Cl^-)_0$, it is possible to derive the expression⁵

$$E = K_1 \{ (LP^+) / [K_1 (ReO_4^-) + K_2 (Cl^-)] \}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (4)$$

when $K_1 (ReO_4^-) \ll K_2 (Cl^-)$, E is independent of the concentration of (ReO_4^-) , but when $K_1 (ReO_4^-) \geq K_2 (Cl^-)$, E should decrease with increasing concentration of perrhenate ion. The results of extraction studies at different initial concentration of Re(VII) are summarized in Table II.

TABLE II

Extraction Coefficients of Re (VII) as a Function of its Initial aqueous phase concentration (with LP^+Cl^- in Nitrobenzene)

Initial Concentration of LP^+Cl^-	$= 1.074 \times 10^{-3} M.$
Volume of each phase	$= 20 \text{ ml.}$
<i>pH</i>	$= 3.9$
Temperature	$= 31^\circ \pm 1^\circ$
Concentration of Re(VII) $\times 10^5$ (in molarity) (M)	Extraction Coefficient (E)
1.074	6356
5.37	6082
10.74	5311
16.1	4750
26.8	2244

Under the experimental conditions employed, K_1 and K_2 are 5.574×10^2 and 9.874×10^{-5} respectively and the condition $K_1 (ReO_4^-) \geq K_2 (Cl^-)$ holds good. Therefore, the decrease in the value of the extraction coefficient of rhenium (VII) with increase in its aqueous phase concentration is in agreement with the prediction of equation 4.

The effect (Table III) of the addition of chloride ions (in the form of neutral salts) on the extraction of rhenium (VII) has been studied. As expected from equation 4, the extraction coefficient of rhenium (VII) decreases with the increasing concentration of chloride ions in the aqueous phase.

5. R. M. Diamond and D. G. Tuck, 'Progress in Inorganic Chemistry', Vol. VI, p. 109, edited by F. A. Cotton, Interscience Publishers Ltd., London, (1960).

TABLE III

Effect of Salts on the Extraction coefficient value of Re (VII) with LP+Cl⁻ in nitrobenzene

Initial concentration of Re (VII)	= $2.15 \times 10^{-5} M$
Initial concentration of LP+Cl ⁻ in Nitrobenzene	= $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$
Volume of each phase	= 20 ml.
pH	= 3.9
Temperature	= $31^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$

Salts	Concentration (in molarity) (M)	Extraction Coefficient (E)
NH ₄ Cl	0.05	6628
	0.10	5093
	0.25	3558
MgCl ₂	0.05	5902
	0.10	3635
	0.25	2500
KNO ₃	0.05	109
	0.10	53
	0.25	19
NaCl	0.05	5736
	0.10	4677
	0.25	2577

Potassium nitrate is more effective than the chlorides in lowering the value of E for rhenium (VII). This is because of the extraction of the ion pair LP+NO₃⁻ into nitrobenzene, which competes with the extraction of LP+ReO₄⁻.

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